

**THE PSYCHOLOGICAL IMPACTS OF LANGUAGE ATTRITION
ON SECOND-GENERATION IMMIGRANTS**

Zokirova Zaynab Zokir qizi,

zokirovazaynab05@gmail.com,

Student, Chirchik State Pedagogical University

Tourism faculty Foreign language and literature:English.

Scientific supervisor: Abduramanova Diana Valeryevna,

Act.assoc.prof.(PhD), Chirchik State Pedagogical University.

Abstract: Language attrition among second-generation immigrants in the U.S. is prevalent and receives scant attention in the field of Applied Psychology. The purpose of this phenomenological investigation was to deepen understanding of the nature of and extent to which language attrition impacts ethnic identity development, sense of belonging, and overall psychological wellbeing. Six focus groups were conducted with a diverse group of 21 second-generation immigrant adults who have one or two foreign-born parents, whose heritage language is other than English, who self-identify as a person of color and have reported a decrease in proficiency in their heritage language over time. Data was collected on the various psycho-social-emotional experiences, attitudes, and needs of second-generation immigrants experiencing heritage language loss.

Keywords: Language, second-generation, language loss, heritage, global citizens, First Language Attrition, IOM.

Language is an emotional, political, social, and economic construct. Language use can be an expression of identity, affiliation, belonging, nationality, and allegiance. It is also often the case that language policies, practices and attitudes are wielded to reproduce unequal power relations, exclude the “other”, maintain superiority, exercise subjugation, and uphold oppressive social stratification. Use and maintenance of heritage language by minoritized groups, especially those in

diaspora, are fraught with the push and pull of political, social, and economic forces. The process of losing mastery or comfort with one's heritage language can produce psychological disequilibrium for many. This study is an investigation of these dynamics and their implications for the field of counseling psychology.

Today's societies are arguably the most globally connected in human history. With the proliferation of modern technology, messages can be sent across the world in a matter of seconds and friendships can be nurtured across space and culture through digital communication tools. Film and music traditions are celebrated cross-culturally. People have the ability to wake up in one country and go to sleep in another in just a matter of hours. Global citizens metaphorically huddle and gather, imagine together, discuss politics, coordinate activism, and produce art. They have more access and capacity to exchange ideas and learn from one another. And yet, at a time with potential for so much integration and interchange among the world communities, the exchange is often imbued with asymmetrical power dynamics [1]. Power systems are built to structure opportunity and assign value differently for people, places, languages, phenotypes, and philosophies. The globe is fastened into intricate power systems that privilege a particular few and dictate who can access resources, who receives and who gives, where and how knowledge flows, whose knowledge is esteemed and elevated, and whose customs, traditions and languages are considered precious and to be preserved and protected.

The authority of cultural, social, and linguistic imperialism is more than simple remnants of the colonial era these forces still rage on today. Thus, the global human community may be closer than they may have ever been, and yet have become increasingly distanced and even more stratified than ever before. This paradox yields complexity in the lived experiences of so many, producing both familiar and new challenges and prospects, including how people grow, navigate identity, belonging and change. Heritage language refers to a non-socially dominant language that is inherited and learned by children in immigrant families and home contexts, but is often never fully developed, lost or confused as children age [2], acculturate and integrate into societally dominant-language spaces.

First Language Attrition also known as Heritage Language Loss describes this process by which a shift of mastery from a minority heritage language to a majority dominant language occurs. This phenomenon tends to affect the second-generation [3], or the children of immigrants, more than any other group and the likelihood for this generation to experience language attrition is higher than for them to be bilingual. The loss of heritage language in second-generation immigrants is a loss that is often intertwined with struggles for identity definition and integration. Second-generation immigrants who are born in the United States often face a constant challenge of construction, reconstruction and renegotiation of ethnic identity, and reconciliation of such identity with other social identities. They often must make sense of their position as perpetual insiders and outsiders in the lands they are meant to call “home.” As a secure sense of identity underpins much research on psychological wellbeing, this investigation strives to illuminate the association between heritage language loss for second-generation immigrants and ethnic identity construction, integration, dissolution, and fragmentation as well as the implications of heritage language/ethnic identity loss and psychological distress and wellbeing.

According to the United Nation’s International Organization of Migration (IOM), there were over 281 million migrants worldwide in 2020, about one in 30 persons in the global population [4]. Though migration has always been part and parcel of the human story, these numbers establish a notable surge over the last half a century. We currently live at a time with the largest number of displaced peoples and/or refugees in recorded history a pattern aggravated by increased geo-political conflicts, widespread identity-based persecution transnationally, and increased displacement by climate crises and economic deprivation. Additionally, the global economy is more integrated and more interdependent than ever, connecting the world’s job market in unique ways and reinforcing global power relations and dynamics. There are several “push and pull factors” that underpin immigration—certainly not all migrant stories are the same, nor are all opportunities, rights, and protections for migrants equal. Human rights are not universally granted in pre-, during or post-migration stages. Access to rights and protections are a function of

the borders that are drawn around place of origin, the intersection of ethnic, racial, religious, and other social identities in a migrant's life and the post migration context of reception [5]. Trauma experienced at one stage in a migrant's life span can affect experiences at another stage. Trauma can also be passed down to second-generation immigrants.

Language may become among the most important sites of conflict where loss is experienced. Heritage language maintenance and loss, thus, may serve as mediator- a crucial factor in the relationship between ethnic identity development and psychological and emotional wellbeing and moderator influencing the strength of that very relationship for this population.

Conclusion

This study aimed to offer an investigation of the phenomenon of language attrition among children of immigrants- an understudied yet widespread experience- and its psychological impacts. It was largely done to support the development of a framework for counselors and researchers to better understand how to support those impacted. The data in this study in many ways affirm previous lines of research that describe the complex social, political, cultural and psychological terrain that so many children of immigrants must navigate living in the United States. An expansion and clear articulation of the nuanced role of heritage language fluency and loss deepens our collective understanding of the crucial role language plays in people's sense ethnic identification, belonging, and wellbeing. Indeed, through this we see how stories that are told, untwisted, and crafted anew have the ability to be vehicles of psychological and social change for individuals, communities and societies.

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